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ORIGINAL PAPER

Does CEO Characteristics affect Dividend Policy?

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Abstract

At present, corporations are spending a lot of energy on establishing an appropriate dividend policy that will bring into balance the needs of present and future stakeholders. Low dividend payout among Nigeria listed consumer-goods firms is a major problem. Dividend policy commands the amount paid out to shareholders by a company. In practice, this is difficult to correctly establish. Can the CEO help in making correct decisions? In this article, we are interested in this question and many more on the characteristics of the CEO. We consider six CEO features: duality, nation, female, tenure, turnover, equity ownership. We construct a dividend policy index from yield, per share, payout, and dividend to asset ratio. We analyze 16 Nigeria listed consumer goods firms for ten years: 2012-2021 (160 dataset) to probe CEOs' influence on dividend policy. Our results show that, consistent with the Agency theory, Nigeria consumer-goods firms' dividend policies are affected by their CEO duality, nationality, gender, tenure, turnover and equity ownership. In addition, listing age and firm size are determinants of dividend policy, however, leverage is not. These results are useful to regulators, shareholders and board of directors in regulating and appointment of firm's CEO. This is among the few studies linking CEO with dividend policy using Nigeria panel data, however, more studies are needed; because the economy is relatively small and unstable.

Keywords: *CEO Characteristics, Chief Executive Officers, Dividend Policy, Listed Consumer-Goods Firms, Nigeria*

Introduction

Dividend is the reward shareholders receive in exchange for their investments in companies in addition to capital gains if any. A firm's policy in this regard is crucial to enable shareholders keep

their investments in companies where such shares are held or look for better investment opportunities elsewhere. Dividend policy (DP) is about monetary policies in respect of paying cash now or enhanced cash payments in the future to the company's shareholders or to reinvest the money into the business so as to take future opportunities. The decision to pay cash dividend or not depends on whether the firm makes sufficient profits or not, because the future is more important for business operations rather than cash dividend payments to existing shareholders. This is because there is no law compelling companies to pay dividend to their shareholders. Although, dividend payment is desirable, the policy whether to pay or not depends on a number of factors. Some of these factors are after tax earnings, cash availability, shareholders' expectation, anticipated future earnings, gearing, return on capital employed, and industry attitudes. However, in this article, emphasis is on the role of CEOs in shaping appropriate dividend policy to enable firms keep shareholders in balance. CEOs are in charge of their corporations' dividend policy. This policy may well determine present and future investors' decisions to invest in the organization. Therefore, the role of the CEO in shaping dividend policy is essential; it is essential because the continued absence of dividend can spell divestments from present shareholders.

Dividend policy is seen through any of these proxies: dividend per share, dividend yield, cash dividend, and dividend to total assets employed in the business. Dividend per share (DPS) is probably the single most important information shareholders would be looking out for in company's financial reports. It is the total sum of dividend declared by a firm on every ordinary or equity share. DPS is obtained by using dividend paid out divided by the number of equity shares. DPS is a reflection of financial performance or profitability given out to shareholders at a particular point in time. It is an information useful to investors, both present and potential in making investment decisions. Similarly, dividend yield follows closely DPS, because it is the fraction of DPS in relation to the share price. It is expressed as a percentage and used often to obtain market capitalization of the firm. Cash dividend as the name involved is the amount of cash paid out as dividend to shareholders. Note that dividend may be paid in equity share bonus if cash payout is not available or is not desirable because new opportunities are preferred to be taken. Finally, dividend to assets as the name implies is the ratio of dividend paid out divided by total assets. It expresses in percentage the reward for each of investment in assets.

The CEO is probably the most recognizable single symbol of corporate governance structure. The power is derived from the board of directors elected or appointed by the shareholders. CEOs usually represent the interest or face of core shareholders. CEOs are the highest ranking officers of their corporations. They represent the public face and they make major decisions. In fact, they are held responsible for the fate of their companies. If the company is doing well, CEOs are heavily rewarded, otherwise, they are traditionally fired and replaced. CEO is the top ranking employee in a business because he/she works for the business. However, in practice, it is unusual to find a CEO that is not appointed by majority shareholders. In large organizations with function corporate governance structure, the CEO comes under regular checks and balances from the board of directors elected or appointed by shareholders. This individual is responsible for the success or failure of the company and he/she is held so religiously.

CEOs characteristics manifest in many forms: female gender, duality, education (expertise), equity ownership, tenure, turnover, and nationality. These form the basis of this article in relation to companies' dividend policy. CEO female gender simply means that the CEO is a woman. CEO

duality refers to instances where the CEO is also the chairman of the board of directors. CEO education also known as expertise refers to the educational background of the CEO, while CEO ownership is used to refer to the number of shares held by the CEO alone as a percentage of total equity shares of the company. CEO tenure refers to the maximum period that the CEO is allowed to remain as head of the company before replacement. CEO turnover refers to the frequency at which the CEO is changed. It is part of good corporate governance requirements that the CEO does not remain in the organization for a long period so that there will be no complacency or compromise. Finally, CEO nationality refers to the country of origin of the head other than Nigeria.

The purpose of this article, therefore, is to assess the effect of CEO characteristics on the dividend policy of Nigeria publicly quoted consumer goods firms. To achieve this, the article determines whether CEO traits have any bearing on the dividend policy of consumer-goods firms? The study is useful to regulators (for policy improvement), shareholders (for performance improvement), and board of directors (for policy formulation and performance improvement). It is also important to mention that further research and body of knowledge in general are enhanced, particularly in specific areas of CEO and dividend policy. As indicated in the literatures, while there are several empirical studies on the nexus between CEOs and dividend policy, this paper contributes heavily to the discussion in Nigeria consumer-goods sector. Also, the choice of the consumer-goods sector for this paper is apt for several reason; first, the sector is probably the most vibrant sector in Nigeria because of its role in providing immediate people's feeding needs. Second, it is the most active on a daily basis since people must eat very day. Third, consumer-goods sector is the single most highly volatile sector with records of CEO turnovers. The paper consists of five sections: introduction, literature and hypotheses, methods, results and discussions, and conclusions and recommendations. The next immediate section deals with conceptual, empirical and theoretical literatures.

Literature Review and Hypotheses

The CEO is the executive officer of a company and as the name suggests he/she has executive powers to make decisions that will move the corporation towards achieving its goals. The CEO is the highest ranking officer of a company. CEOs are in charge of expansion, profitability and improving share prices in order to create capital gains for shareholders. CEOs have remarkable influence in their companies, including the decision to pay dividend or not depending on the current or future focus of top management. CEOs perform several functions including setting and executing firm strategy, building senior management team, making capital allocation decisions, setting vision, mission, goals, objectives and values, and communicating with shareholders through the board or directly.

The decisions regarding dividend payout or not is usually that of the CEO and executive directors. Dividend policy is a symbol of balance between past and future investments as seen by top management. It is what a firm used to structure its dividend payment to equity holders and the regularity with which the dividends are effected. Dividend policy implies any one of these four positions: regular payment of dividend, stable dividend payment, irregular payment or no dividend payment at all. It is necessary to note that a dividend is the share of profits that is distributed to equity-holders or the return equity-holders receive in exchange for their investments in the organization. Two types of dividend are common: cash dividend and bonus shares. Cash dividend arises when dividend is paid out in cash usually on account of excess liquidity. Bonus shares refer

to shares distributed to equity-holders either under liquidity difficulty or in addition to cash dividend. The next section discusses the empirical literature linking the CEO with dividend policy.

Feng et al. (2007) examined CEO and dividend policy and found significant impact on DP. Also, Asamoah (2011) examined corporate governance and DP in Ghana and found that CEO duality influence firm's DP. Bolbol (2012) examined board characteristics and dividend payout of 50 Malaysian construction for 2010. They observed that CEO duality and dividend payout are significantly negatively correlated. Uwalomwa et al. (2015) investigated the relationship between corporate governance mechanisms and the dividend payout policies of 50 Nigeria listed firms for the period 2006-2011. Findings revealed that CEO duality and DP have significant positive effect. Chuah et al. (2015) investigated corporate governance and DP using 182 companies in Malaysia for 2009 to 2013. They found CEO duality and DP negatively insignificantly related.

Shahid et al. (2016) examined CEO duality and dividend policy of 176 and 280 companies from KSE and BSI from 2010-2015 and discovered a negative association. Also, Mehdi et al. (2017) studied the impact of board governance on dividend policy in emerging markets of 362 non-financial listed firms from East Asian and Gulf Cooperation Council countries. They concluded that dividend decision is inversely related to CEO duality. Adjaoud and Hermassi (2017) investigated the impact of CEO duality on the dividend policy of Canadian firms listed on the Toronto Stock Exchange over the period 2008-2011. The results showed that dividend payouts and the likelihood to pay dividends were impacted significantly by CEO duality. Elmagrhi et al. (2017) examined board characteristics and dividend pay-out ratio from 2010 to 2013 and suggested that CEO duality do not have any significant effect.

Bangun et al. (2018) analyzed the effect of corporate governance on dividend policy of 95 manufacturing companies listed in Indonesia Stock Exchange for the period 2014-2016. CEO duality do not have a significant effect on dividend policy. Bista et al. (2019) examined corporate governance and dividend policy of 14 Nepalese banks and 7 insurance companies from 2010–2011 to 2015–2016. They reported that the beta coefficients for CEO duality, firm size, gender diversity, and leverage are positive. In Pakistan, Mirza and Malik (2019) evaluated corporate governance and DP of listed companies from 2010 to 2017. Results depicted that CEO duality is positively significant. In Jordan, Aloudat et al. (2019) investigated CEO duality and DP of 30 industrial companies during 2007-2017. The result of the study revealed that duality of CEO and chairman position was found to have no effect on DP.

Benjamin and Biswas (2019) examined CEO duality and dividend policy of S&P 1500 firms for 2010-2015. The results showed that gender positively impacts DPE. Further, Suwaidana and Khalaf (2020) examined board composition and DP of manufacturing companies for 2013–2015. The results identified duality and DP to be expressively negatively connected. Tahir et al. (2020) examined the extent to which corporate board attributes influence dividend payout policies of 2,842 firm's year-observations of Malaysian non-financial firms from 2005 to 2018. The results revealed that CEO duality and DP are positively-statistically related. Duong et al. (2020) analysed the impacts of board gender diversity in the Vietnam market and illustrated that female CEO and female CEO duality decrease the dividend ratio. El-Ammari (2021) examined the effects of CEO duality on DP in Tunisia over 576 firm-year observations for period 1996–2019. The findings of this research indicated that there was a positive effect of CEO duality on DP. Tijjani and Ishaku

(2022) examined the effect of board characteristics on dividend payout ratio of listed Nigerian deposit money banks for 2004 to 2013. It was found that separate CEOs and Chairmen of their boards had positively impacted on dividend payout ratio. In view of these mixed results, we suggest that:

H₁: CEO duality and DP are significantly related.

In addition, Jalbert et al. (2007) scrutinized CEOs' nation influenced dividend policy. The data for the study was derived from the Forbes 800 CEO compensation data for 1991-1997 and included 4,834 observations. CEOs from Central and South America were better paid dividends than other CEOs. Mirza and Malik (2019) evaluated corporate governance and DP in Pakistan for 2010 to 2017. Results depicted that CEO nationality and DP are positively significant. Aloudat et al. (2019) investigated CEO nationality and DP of 30 Jordanian industrial companies for 2007-2017. The result revealed that nationality of CEO was found to have no effect on DP.

Naseem and Khurram (2020) used a sample of 15,818 firm year observations over the 1996-2015 period to examine the impact of CEOs cultural background on dividend policy. They found that foreign CEOs are more likely to pay dividends. Kumshe et al. (2020) examined CEO nationality and DP of 20 companies from Kenya, Nigeria and South Africa for 2012 to 2016. CEO nationality and DP were found to be significantly interrelated. Mohy-Ud-Din et al. (2022) considered nationality and dividend policy of 77 firms for 2012-2019. The study suggested that firms involved with diverse nationality was significantly associated with DP. Khan et al. (2022) investigated the impact of board demographic diversity on the dividend payout policy in 67 non-financial companies listed on Borsa Istanbul 100 index from 2013 to 2018. The result indicated that nationality played an influential role in encouraging companies to pay high dividends. In view of these mixed results, it is proposed that:

H₂: CEO nationality has significant impact on DP.

Bolbol (2012) also found that gender was negatively insignificantly correlated with dividend payout. Further, McGuinness et al. (2015) examined gender of CEO and dividends in China and observed minor difference in dividend distributions concerning opposite gender. Al-Dhamari et al. (2016) investigated the effect of gender on dividend payout policy. They found that women's presence on boards has positive impact on dividend yield (dividend payout). Elmagrhi et al. (2017) also showed that board gender diversity has a significant negative relationship with the level of dividend pay-out. Benjamin and Biswas (2019) examined whether CEO gender composition affects dividend policy. Using S&P 1500 firms from 2010-2015, the results showed that gender and DP are positively related. Kumshe et al. (2020) also examined CEO gender and DP; CEO gender was found not to be significant. Nwidobie (2020) assessed CEO gender diversity and DP of 9 Nigeria quoted non-financial companies for 2010-2018 and found that increasing the proportion of females on the boards of these firms negatively influences dividend.

Thompson and Manu (2021) examined whether female presence and DP were interrelated and the result showed that female presence has a strong positive significant effect on the likelihood of dividend declaration. Ain et al. (2021) investigated gender diversity on the board and DP in China for 2003–2017. Their results showed that gender diversity on the board is positively associated with DP. Mohy-Ud-Din et al. (2022) investigated CEO gender and DP of 77 firms during 2012-2019. The study suggested that firms involved with female gender is significantly associated with

DP. Khan et al. (2022) also found gender was insignificant in affecting dividend payments. In view of these mixed results, it is proposed that:

H₃: CEO gender has significant impact on DP.

Ghosh and Sirmans (2006) tested the hypothesis that dividend payout levels reflect the influence of CEO tenure. Their analyses indicated that dividend payout and dividend yield are functions of CEO tenure. Furthermore, Feng et al. (2007) examined the relationship between CEO tenure and dividend policy of real estate investment trusts. Their analyses showed positive connection between CEO tenure and DP. McGuinness et al. (2015) examined CEO tenure and DP. CEO tenure bear a strong positive association with cash distributions. Chuah et al. (2015) also found CEO tenure and DP positively significant.

Onali et al. (2016) investigated CEO tenure and DP for 109 European quoted banks for 2005–2013 and CEO tenure and DP had negative impact. Kumshe et al. (2020) observed CEO tenure and DP and CEO tenure was found not to be significant. Briano-Turrent et al. (2020) investigated family-CEOs, CEO demographics and DP in Latin America. They showed that CEO tenure has a consistent and significant negative effect on the dividend payout. Madyan et al. (2021) examined the effect of CEO tenure on DP of 93 non-financial family firms listed in Indonesia for 2013-2017. The findings showed that CEO tenure does not significantly strengthen the positive effect on dividend payout ratios. Khan et al. (2022) also found gender, tenure are insignificant in affecting dividend payments. In view of these mixed results, it is proposed that:

H₄: CEO tenure has significant effect on DP.

Also, Onali et al. (2016) found CEO turnover and DP with negative impact. Santos (2019) assessed CEO turnover and DP of 394 firms from 2004-2017 and concluded that CEO turnover increased firms' dividend. Barros et al. (2021) provided evidence of CEO turnover and DP and concluded that companies more likely to pay dividends after a CEO turnover. In view of these mixed results, it is proposed that:

H₅: CEO turnover has significant influence on DP.

Schooley and Barney (1994) examined dividends and chief executive officer (CEO) stock ownership as interrelated mechanisms. They found a significant nonmonotonic relation between dividend yield and CEO stock ownership. Further, Ghosh and Sirmans (2006) also observed that dividend payout is affected by CEO ownership of company shares. Wen and Jia (2010) studied the dividend policies of bank holding companies which have dispersed ownership in a regulated environment. The results showed that dividend is negatively related to CEO ownership. Also, McGuinness et al. (2015) examined the association between Chinese stock issuers' CEO ownership and dividend cash payout. Cash pay-out was found to be increasing in directors' equity stakes. Chuah et al. (2015) found CEO ownership and DP negatively insignificant. Onali et al. (2016) also showed that CEO ownership and DP negatively impact. Kumshe et al. (2020) studied CEO share ownership and DP and reported significant relationship. Madyan et al. (2021) examined CEO ownership and dividend policy and reported a positive effect. In view of these mixed results, it is proposed that:

H₆: CEO share ownership has significant influence on DP.

In terms of the control variables, Slimani (2009) found that size is the major factor that differentiates between paying-dividend and non-paying-dividend firms though large firms are likely to pay dividends. Bolbol (2012) also found that corporate size and DP were insignificantly positive; leverage was insignificantly and negatively correlated with DP. Adjaoud and Hermassi (2017) confirmed the significant role of firm size and leverage on DP. Also, Mirza and Malik (2019) found that both firm size and leverage negatively affect DP. Aloudat et al. (2019) revealed that firm size and financial leverage have no effect on DP. Madyan et al. (2021) also found that leverage and firm size significantly affect the DP, but firm age does not.

Several theories have been used to explain the CEO and firm's dividend policy: the agency theory, stakeholders' theory, signaling theory, capital need theory, stewardship theory and resource-based theory. In this article, agency theory provided theoretical basis. Agency theory is a philosophy that is used to explain and resolve issues in the connection between principals and their agents. As indicated before, the principals are the shareholders and the agents are the CEOs. The agent is seen to represent the principal in all business transactions carried out by the CEO on behalf of the company. The CEO simply derives his/her powers from the shareholders because they appoint/elect or dismiss the agent whenever the need arises.

Methods

The CEO characteristics used in this paper are commonly found in empirical literatures and are available at Machameratio database: tenure, duality, gender, turnover, share ownership and nationality. Dividend policy is represented by an index derived from four measures of the policy: DPS, dividend yield, cash dividend payment, and dividend to total assets. This study is among the earliest articles to use dividend policy index. A sample of 16 consumer-goods firms was used. The empirical data was obtained from Machameratio database and tested with descriptive statistics, correlation matrix, regression and diagnostics. A priori expectations are that all proxies of the CEO are related positively with dividend policy. An econometric model was developed to account for all proxies of the CEO in relation with dividend policy.

$$DP_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CEOT_{i,t} + \beta_2 CEOD_{i,t} + \beta_3 CEOG_{i,t} + \beta_4 CEOTR_{i,t} + \beta_5 CEOO_{i,t} + \beta_6 CEON_{i,t} + \beta_7 LEVG_{i,t} + \beta_8 LAGE_{i,t} + \beta_9 FSIZ_{i,t} + \epsilon_{i,t}$$

Whereas:

DP = Dividend policy index derived from the sum of DPS, cash dividend, dividend yield and dividend to total assets divided by 4 (Kumshe et al., 2020; Tahir et al., 2020; Yahaya, 2017).

CEOT = CEO tenure measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to companies with CEOs that have stay for 3 years or "0" for less (Kumshe et al., 2020; Yahaya & Awen, 2021).

CEOD = CEO duality measured as a dummy where "1" is assigned to companies that have a CEO that is separated from the chairman and "0" for otherwise (Yahaya & Awen, 2021).

CEOG = CEO female gender measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to corporations with Female CEOs and "0" for else (Kumshe et al., 2020; Tahir et al., 2020; Yahaya & Awen, 2021).

CEOTR = CEO turnover measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to companies with new CEOs and "0" for else (Kumshe et al., 2020; Tahir et al., 2020; Yahaya & Awen, 2021).

CEOO = CEO share ownership measured as number of CEO shares divided by total numbers of shares (Kumshe et al., 2020; Tahir et al., 2020; Yahaya & Awen, 2021).

CEON = CEO nationality measured as dummy where "1" is assigned in case of foreign CEOs and "0" for else (Kumshe et al., 2020; Tahir et al., 2020; Yahaya & Awen, 2021).

LEVG = Leverage (Onwe et al., 2020; Yahaya & Andow, 2015; Yahaya et al., 2019; Yahaya & Tijjani, 2021a; Yahaya & Tijjani, 2021b).

LAGE = Listing firm age (Agboola et al., 2020; Yahaya & Tijjani, 2021; Yeosuf et al., 2017).

FSIZ = Firm size (Agboola et al., 2020; Yahaya, 2006; Yahaya & Tijjani, 2021; Yeosuf et al., 2017)

i, t = Firms, time (13 consumer goods firms, 10 years)

β_0 = Autonomous

β_{1-9} = Coefficients

ε = Miscalculation

Results and Discussions

This section begins with the descriptive statistics of the variables used in the paper and ends with the final regression model after accounting for the diagnostics.

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
DP	160	7.085	6.209	0	21.269
CEOD	160	.919	.274	0	1
CEON	160	.263	.441	0	1
CEOG	160	.019	.136	0	1
CEOT	160	.681	.467	0	1
CEOTR	160	.194	.396	0	1
CEO	160	2.551	6.772	0	25.081
LEVG	160	.762	.22	.315	2.478
LAGE	160	26.9	11.901	2	48
FSIZ	160	7.653	.509	5.97	9.03

Source: Extracts from STATA 14

As shown in the table, the data is balanced for 160 observations. Dividend policy averages 7.085 with standard deviation from the central mean of 6.209 and smallest and highest mean of 0 and 21.269, respectively. CEO duality averages .919 with standard deviation from the central mean of .274 and smallest and highest mean of 0 and 1. Further, CEO nationality averages .263 with standard deviation from the central mean of .441 and smallest and highest mean of 0 and 1. CEO gender averages .019 with standard deviation from the central mean of .136 and smallest and highest mean of 0 and 1. Similarly, CEO tenure averages .681 with standard deviation from the central mean of .467 and smallest and highest mean of 0 and 1. CEO turnover averages .194 with standard deviation from the central mean of .396 and smallest and highest mean of 0 and 1. Finally, CEO ownership averages 2.551 with standard deviation from the central mean of 6.772 and smallest and highest mean of 0 and 25.1. On the control variables, leverage averages .762 with standard deviation from the central mean of .22 and smallest and highest mean of .315 and 2.478. Also, listing age averages 27 years with standard deviation from the central mean of 12 years and smallest and highest mean of 2 years and 48 years. Further, firm size averages 7.653 with standard deviation from the central mean of .509 and smallest and highest mean of 5.97 and 9.03. Table 2 presents the results of correlation analysis.

Table 2
Pairwise Correlation Matrix

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)
(1) DP	1.000									
(2) CEOD	0.015 (0.853)	1.000								
(3) CEON	0.247* (0.002)	0.177* (0.025)	1.000							
(4) CEOG	0.019 (0.809)	0.041 (0.606)	-0.082 (0.300)	1.000						
(5) CEOT	0.057 (0.476)	-0.007 (0.929)	-0.049 (0.537)	-0.202* (0.010)	1.000					
(6) CEOTR	-0.007 (0.933)	0.146 (0.066)	0.031 (0.697)	0.282* (0.000)	-0.649* (0.000)	1.000				
(7) CEOO	0.005 (0.951)	0.112 (0.158)	-0.225* (0.004)	-0.052 (0.512)	0.229* (0.004)	-0.167* (0.035)	1.000			
(8) LEVG	0.014 (0.860)	-0.102 (0.198)	-0.135 (0.089)	0.044 (0.584)	-0.020 (0.803)	0.021 (0.790)	0.368* (0.000)	1.000		
(9) LAGE	-0.218* (0.006)	-0.118 (0.137)	-0.057 (0.472)	0.059 (0.455)	0.130 (0.102)	-0.142 (0.072)	0.055 (0.493)	-0.065 (0.417)	1.000	
(10) FSIZ	-0.209* (0.008)	0.141 (0.074)	-0.035 (0.660)	0.175* (0.027)	0.045 (0.576)	-0.006 (0.938)	-0.089 (0.261)	-0.076 (0.338)	0.389* (0.000)	1.000

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: Extracts from STATA 14

In summary, Table 2 indicates that CEO duality, gender, tenure, and share ownership are positively related with DP; while nationality is significantly positively related with DP and turnover is negatively related with DP. For control variables, leverage positively related with DP, while listing age and firm size are negatively related with DP. Table 3 reports the results of ordinary least square regression.

Table 3
Ordinary least square regression

DP	Coef.	St.Err.	t-val.	p-val.	[95% Interval]	Sig
CEOD	-.987	1.887	-0.52	.602	-4.715 2.741	
CEON	3.717	1.128	3.30	.001	1.489 5.946	***
CEOG	4.482	3.685	1.22	.226	-2.799 11.764	
CEOT	1.667	1.35	1.23	.219	-1.001 4.335	
CEOTR	.428	1.625	0.26	.793	-2.782 3.639	
CEOO	.041	.082	0.51	.613	-.12 .203	
LEVG	.112	2.364	0.05	.962	-4.559 4.783	
LAGE	-.089	.045	-2.01	.046	-.177 -.001	**
FSIZ	-1.773	1.053	-1.68	.094	-3.853 .307	*
Constant	21.5	7.802	2.76	.007	6.085 36.915	***
R-squared		0.142	Number of obs		160	
F-test		2.748	Prob > F		0.005	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Source: Extracts from STATA 14

It is vital to note that the essence of carrying out OLS regression at this stage is to allow for regression diagnostics. The results of these checks are presented in Tables 4-9 and Figure 1.

Figure 1: *Checking for unusual and influential data*

Source: Extracts from STATA 14

Figure 1 shows that there are no unusual or influential data that requires transformation. Table 4 presents the results of checking normality of residual.

Table 4

Shapiro-Wilk W test for normal data

Variable	Obs	W	V	z	Prob>z
e	160	0.973	3.325	2.733	0.003

Source: Extracts from STATA 14

It obvious from the results in Table 4 that the residual is not normally distributed. Therefore, the results in Table 5 indicate the form of transformation that is required.

Table 5

Data Transformation Options

Transformation	formula	chi ² (2)	P(chi ²)
cubic	e ³	49.83	0.000
square	e ²	24.05	0.000
identity	e	6.33	0.042
square root	sqrt(e)	5.42	0.067
log	log(e)	4.93	0.085
1/(square root)	1/sqrt(e)	7.60	0.022
inverse	1/e	19.16	0.000
1/square	1/(e ²)	56.74	0.000
1/cubic	1/(e ³)	.	0.000

Source: Extracts from STATA 14

From the results in Table 5, two forms of data transformation would make the residual to be normally distributed: square root and log normal. We use log normal (.085) because it has the least chi². We equally test for signs of multicollinearity and the results are reported in Table 6.

Table 6
Checking for multicollinearity

	VIF	1/VIF
CEOTR	1.881	.532
CEOT	1.806	.554
CEO	1.389	.72
FSIZ	1.301	.769
LAGE	1.273	.785
LEVG	1.223	.818
CEOD	1.212	.825
CEOG	1.140	.878
CEON	1.123	.89
Mean VIF	1.372	.

Source: Extracts from STATA 14

As indicated in Table 6, there is no evidence to support multicollinearity among the independent and control variables. We also test for evidence of heteroskedasticity and the results are contained in Table 7.

Table 7
Checking homoscedasticity of residual

Source	chi2	df	p
Heteroskedasticity	57.560	40	0.035
Skewness	30.300	9	0.000
Kurtosis	7.300	1	0.007
Total	95.160	50	0.000

Source: Extracts from STATA 14

Table 7 clearly indicates that there is heteroskedasticity in the model. This requires that the final regression use robustness test. We test for model specification error and the results are presented in Table 8.

Table 8
Model specification error

Source	SS	df	MS	Number	of	obs	=	160
Model	867.640	2	433.820	Prob	>	F	=	0.00
Residual	262.046	157	33.516	R2	=	0.141		
Total	6129.686	159	38.551	Root	MSE	=	5.789	
DP	Coef.	Std.Err.	t	P>t	[95%Con	Interval]		
_hat	0.926	1.101	0.840	0.401	-1.248	3.100		
_hatsq	0.005	0.071	0.070	0.946	-0.135	0.145		
_cons	0.254	4.002	0.060	0.950	-7.650	8.158		

Ramsey RESET test using powers of the fitted values of DP

Ho: model has no omitted variables

F(3, 147) = 2.57

Prob > F = 0.0564

Source: Extracts from STATA 14

Taken the results of linktest and omitted variables test together, the model has no specification error and omitted variables. We test for the presence of panel effects in the model and the results are reported in Table 9.

Table 9

Panel effects

	Var	Sd = sqrt (Var)
DP	38.55148	6.208984
e	22.36554	4.729222
u	20.70277	4.550029
Chibar ² (01)	57.95	
Prob > chibar ²	.000	

Source: Extracts from STATA 14

Table 9 clearly showed a panel effect, this calls for determination of which panel model effects is a most appropriate. The results of Hausman Specification Test shows that the chi²(9) is 12.93 and the Prob>chi² is 0.1660; a clear indication that the appropriate model is random effects. The results of the final regression model which accounts for heteroskedasticity and panel effects in the model are contained in Table 10.

Use REM

Table 10

Final Regression results

NDP	Coef.	St.Err.	t-val	p-val	[95% Interval]	Sig
CEOD	-.176	.019	-9.18	.000	-.214 - .138	***
CEON	.511	.04	12.86	.000	.433 .589	***
CEOG	.714	.042	16.92	.000	.631 .797	***
CEOT	.275	.026	10.68	.000	.225 .326	***
CEOTR	.053	.023	2.35	.019	.009 .098	**
CEO	.007	.001	10.36	.000	.005 .008	***
LEVG	.014	.018	0.77	.440	-.022 .05	
LAGE	-.013	.001	-17.32	.000	-.015 -.012	***
FSIZ	-.239	.026	-9.05	.000	-.29 -.187	***
Constant	3.87	.196	19.72	.000	3.486 4.255	***
Overall r ²		0.969	No. of obs		160	
Chi-square		1175.036	Prob > chi ²		0.000	
R ² within		0.947	R ² between		0.989	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Source: Extracts from STAT 14

The results of the final regression indicate that beta coefficient of CEO duality, listing age and firm size are negative. Also, the beta coefficients of CEO nationality, gender, tenure, turnover, equity ownership, and leverage are positive. These results imply greater values for DP. Further, note that all the proxies of CEO characteristics used in this study are significant in power with respect to dividend policy. These results are consistent with the works of Feng et al. (2007), Asamoah (2011), Bolbol (2012), Uwalomwa et al. (2015), Mirza and Malik (2019), Suwaidana and Khalf (2020), Tahir et al. (2020), Kumshe et al. (2020) and Mohy-Ud-Din et al. (2022) among several others. However, they are inconsistent with the works of Chuah et al. (2015), Elmagrhi et al. (2017) and Bangun et al. (2018) to mention few of them. In view of these results, all the hypotheses are hereby accepted. The model used is fit because its $\text{Prob} > \chi^2$ is .000. The overall model R^2 is .969 percent, meaning that the part of variations in dividend policy explained by the characteristics of the CEO is 96.9 percent.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This article examines the effects of CEO characteristics on the dividend policy of Nigeria public listed consumer-goods firms. In line with the agency theory, the results confirmed that CEO is a determinant of firm's dividend policy among Nigeria listed consumer-goods companies. Also, listing age and firm size are determinants as well, however, gearing is not. The findings are limited to Nigeria publicly quoted consumer-goods firms; so the choice of sector is debatable as other sectors are equally important. Also, the results are based on the methods adopted in this article. The model is not error-free, therefore, using more variables is a better possibility. The paper calls for more studies to investigate the relationship between corporate CEOs and dividend policy in the case of Nigeria by testing data from all the sectors and for longer periods. In terms of policies, CEO duality should be discouraged as applied to banks today in Nigeria due to its lack of transparency and accountability. However, CEO nationality, gender, tenure, turnover and share ownership should be strengthened.

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